

SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pARTicle Data (SPEARHEAD)

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Identifications of radio, hard X-rays and gamma-ray

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List of Acronyms

AIA	The Atmospheric Imaging Assembly (of SDO)
CME	Coronal Mass Ejection
ERNE	Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and electron Experiment (on-board SOHO)
EU	European Union
EUI	Extrem Ultraviolet Imager on Solar Orbiter
GBM	The Fermi Gamma-ray Burst Monitor
GLE	Ground Level Enhancement
LAT	The Fermi Large Area Telescope
MHD	MagnetoHydroDynamic
PSP	Parker Solar Probe
RHESSI	Reuven Ramaty High Energy Solar Spectroscopic Imager
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SDO	Solar Dynamics Observatory
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
STEREO	Solar-Terrestrial Relations Observatory
STIX	Spectrometer Telescope for Imaging X-rays of Solar Orbiter
SPEARHEAD	SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data
WP	Work Package
GOES	Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
WISPR	Wide Imager of PSP

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document outlines the first results of the systematic analysis work carried out to provide the solar context of the $>100\text{MeV}$ Solar Energetic Particle (SEP) events listed provided by deliverable D5.1 with complete coverage of solar cycles 23 and 24, while also covering the ongoing solar cycle 25. In sub-task 4.1.1, the 169 SEPs were considered individually and a systematic search was carried out to derive the solar signatures of the SEPs. We analysed energetic electromagnetic radiation (soft X-rays, hard X-rays and gamma rays) as well as radio waves in search for type II and type III bursts and CME signatures in white-light imagery. In preparation for deliverable D4.3 due on month 36 we have also included information on 3-D shock fitting. This provides important complementary information to the the first catalogue of the SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data (SPEARHEAD) project, funded by the Horizon Europe Framework Programme of the European Union (EU). The last part of the deliverable, associated with sub-task 4.1.2, presents more in-depth analysis of two powerful SEP events added in 2024 to the $>100\text{ MeV}$ catalogue. This includes work presented at the ESWW 2024 in Coimbra, Portugal.

1 Introduction

The electromagnetic properties of the candidate solar sources of the different SEPs provide important information on the acceleration of SEPs in the solar atmosphere as well as their transport from the Sun to the points of in situ measurements. A review of the available radio, hard X-rays and gamma ray data for the events selected in Task 4-1 is on-going.

Two main tasks are underway:

- *Sub-task 4.1.1:* one consisting in providing an estimate of the solar source to each intense SEP listed in the ERNE and EPHIN SEP catalogues provided by WP5
- *Sub-task 4.1.2:* In-depth analyses of the events given in the previous table for a subset of events of particular interest to the science of particle acceleration and transport.

2 Solar Associations For the >100 MeV SEP catalogue

A catalogue of Solar Energetic Particle (SEP) events, based on a systematic scan of proton data at >100 MeV observed by Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO) / Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and electron Experiment (ERNE) over the years 1997–2024 has been compiled within SPEARHEAD and corresponds to the first deliverable of WP5 (Vainio et al. 2024, hereafter D5.1). A total of 169 proton events were identified and analyzed, while, solar associations were identified. Fig. 1 presents the number of the identified events as a function of time, underlying the extent of the catalogue covering solar cycles (SC) 23, 24 and the current SC25 as shown by the evolution of the number of the SEP events, as well as, the lack of >100 MeV proton events at the beginning of SC24.

Figure 1: Distribution of the >100 SEP events of the SPEARHEAD catalogue as a function of time in years.

2.1 Identifications of soft X-rays flares:

Soft X-rays are important to consider because they are associated to one of the two main accelerators of SEPs, i.e flares. The strongest solar flares are usually related to fast and wide CMEs and powerful SEPs. The intensity of the soft X-ray flare is correlated with the speed of CMEs and their shocks (Jarry et al. 2023) and the intensity of SEP events (see e.g. Papaioannou et al. 2016; Kouloumvakos et al. 2019).

2.1.1 Instruments:

Figure 2: Soft X-ray flare measurements in 0.5-4.0 Å (blue) and 1.0-8.0 Å (red) by the GOES-15 instruments between 16 May 2012 and 18 May 2012. The thresholds for the different flare classes are shown. This plot is taken directly from the Propagation Tool (Rouillard et al. 2017).

The main source of soft X-ray flare measurements is the Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite (GOES), operated by the United States' National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA). 16 GOES satellites have now been operated since October 1975. GOES records solar soft X-rays in the 1-8 Angstrom (0.1-0.8 nm) and 0.5-4.0 Angstrom (0.05-0.4 nm) which constitute the primary basis of flare classification. The smallest are B-class, followed by C, M and X, the largest. A flare class corresponds to x-ray fluxes exceeding certain thresholds.

2.1.2 Methodology:

The association was done manually via a direct inspection of the soft X-ray flare time series together with the aid of advanced data visualisation tools including the IRAP Propagation Tool (Rouillard et al. 2017). For each of the 169 SEP events in the > 100 MeV catalogue, we used the onset time of each event provided in the catalogue given by WP5 which was entered in the Propagation Tool interface shown in Figure 3. In its "SEP propagation mode", the tool automatically fetches the speed of the solar wind measured in situ at the SEP onset time to compute the shape of the Parker spiral all the way to the solar surface. This approach ignores the detailed modelling of the solar corona (see "Future improvements" below). By giving the tool a particle energy and type, it then provides an estimate of the onset time by assuming a ballistic scatter-free propagation.

We then searched for solar flares that occurred around or **before** that estimated onset time within a broad surface search area defined by the extent of the active region belt. The flare association was then established with the strongest flare that occurred in that search area and near the onset time. For the majority of the SEP events, a clear flare stood out and could be easily selected. However for some events, several flares occurred either simultaneously or in rapid succession, and we could not make a straightforward association. These events were flagged as "Uncertain" at this stage and will have to be revisited in the future.

Figure 3: Illustration of the use of the IRAP Propagation Tool to connected in situ measurements of SEPs with soft X-ray flares. Left-hand panel: the different components of the tool are: a view of the ecliptic plane with probes and planets of the inner heliosphere. Top-right panel: a solar surface magnetogram with the position of magnetic connectivity points, solar flares and the search area. Bottom right panel: the interface to enter the SEP onset time given from WP5, the energy set here at 100 MeV, the speed of the solar wind measured in situ that defines the shape of the Parker spiral.

2.1.3 Data entries into the catalogue:

For each successful soft X-ray flare association, we registered the start time of the flare, the time of its peak value, its class, position and the instrument that made the measurement. These entries are shown in Figure 4. Events for which an association could not be established because the flare occurred on the far side of the Sun are labelled as “far side events” with ‘/’ markers in the other entries. 34 instances of such far-side events were recorded out of the currently 169 events. Cases for which too many flares occurred simultaneously and an association could therefore not be established are marked as “U” for Unclear with similar markers in the table. Cases for which the flare location was not made available automatically by NOAA were flagged as “TBD” for future work (see the relevant section below).

2.1.4 First Results

Figure 5 presents some interesting initial results based on the association work between the $>100\text{MeV}$ catalogue and soft X-ray flare characteristics. We show the longitudes of the identified flaring sources (72%, 122/169 events). Among the identified sources, 34 are far side events, i.e that it will not be possible to identify them. For the 13 others, which are not present in the published (precedently described) catalogues, we hope to be able to obtain their location by inspecting the imagery. The flare longitudes are comprised between -89° and 132° , with a mean of 48.87° and a median of 54.5° . This demonstrates that an optimal magnetic connection of the source to the Earth is an important condition for particles to

SOHO/ERNE > 100 MeV S ID		X-ray flare							
No	Identifier	Start		Peak		Class	Position	Observer	
		Date	Time	Date	Time				
98	20120307T014500	2012-03-07	00:13	2012-03-07	00:24	X7.8	N17E27	GOES-15	
99	20120313T174000	2012-03-13	17:12	2012-03-13	17:41	X1.1	N17W66	GOES-15	
100	20120517T014500	2012-05-17	01:25	2012-05-17	01:47	M7.3	N11W76	GOES-15	
101	20120706T233000	2012-07-06	23:01	2012-07-06	23:08	X1.6	S13W59	GOES-15	
102	20120712T150500	2012-07-12	16:16	2012-07-12	16:52	X2.0	S15W01	GOES-15	
103	20120717T160000	2012-07-17	12:19	2012-07-17	17:15	M2.5	S23W61	GOES-15	
104	20120719T062000	2012-07-19	04:17	2012-07-19	05:59	X1.1	S13W88	GOES-15	
105	20120723T072500	/	/	/	/	far side event	S17W132	/	

Figure 4: Extract of the catalogue entries related to the soft X-ray flare associations.

Figure 5: Statistics on the identified flaring sources of the >100MeV catalogue (72%, 122/169 events). Panel on the left: distribution of the flare longitude in Stonyhurst heliographic coordinates. Panel on the right: distribution of the flare magnitude, i.e the maximum intensity measured for the events.

be recorded in-situ, especially particles at an energy of >100 MeV. The mean of the soft X-ray flares magnitude is $2.78 \times 10^{-4} \text{ W/m}^2$, whereas its minimum and maximum are respectively $2.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ W/m}^2$ and $2.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ W/m}^2$. The median of the sample is $1.05 \times 10^{-4} \text{ W/m}^2$. This highlights the fact that strong SEP events are primarily associated with strong (>M-class) flares. Figure 6 presents the timing difference between the peak of the soft X-ray flare and the beginning of the >100MeV proton event. This result is preliminary because, as mentioned in the Deliverable D5.1, the event onset sometimes did not reflect reality due to e.g. data gaps. Thus, by supposition, there should be no events with a negative delay here. However, three events showed a strongly negative timing difference, indicating a late onset estimation due to data gaps in SOHO/ERNE. As they prevented us from reading correctly the statistics showed, we decided to remove them. These events are the 29, 82 and 112 in the catalogue, i.e

Figure 6: Timing difference (hours in UT) between SEP event onset determined with SOHO/ERNE and soft X-ray peak intensity of the associated flare.

respectively the 10 August 2001, the 5 December 2006 and the 12 October 2013. Figure 6 presents that the majority of the [SEP](#) events occurred during the impulsive phase of the associated flares ([Benz 1993](#)) with another fraction of them being associated to their decay phase, preliminary indicating acceleration processes at play, which is one of the scientific questions of [SPEARHEAD](#).

2.1.5 Future improvements:

Future developments of this work could consist in:

- **Missing flare locations:** events for which the timing and intensity of the flare were available but not its location because it was not automatically provided by the NOAA automated alert systems (13 events in our catalogue). These events will be revisited in the future and a dedicated analysis will exploit extreme ultraviolet imaging from either the Extreme Ultraviolet Imaging Telescope (EIT) on SoHO or the Atmospheric Imaging Assembly (AIA) instrument on the Solar Dynamics Observatory (SDO) to locate the flare directly in the images.
- **Far-side events:** the exploitation of soft X-ray measurements by the X-Ray Spectrometer ([Schlemm et al. 2007](#)) onboard the MESSENGER spacecraft which would complement the present nicely at times when MESSENGER was directly observing the far side of the Sun from Earth's perspective. This would not be too challenging to carry out for the identified 34 far-side events.
- **Magnetic Connectivity Analysis:** a more through study of magnetic connectivity between the spacecraft measured the > 100 MeV [SEPs](#) and the low solar corona. By incorporating global modelling of the solar atmosphere we could provide a more detailed assessment of the proximity or not of the identified flare to the estimated source region of [SEPs](#). This work would exploit IRAP's widely used Magnetic Connectivity Tool ([Rouillard et al. 2020a](#)).

2.2 Identification of type III radio bursts

Radio bursts are classified into five different categories or types (from I to V) based on their properties in frequency-time spectrograms ([Wild et al. 1963](#)). The most common coherent radio emission from the Sun are type III bursts (see e.g. [Reid 2020](#), and references therein). Type III radio bursts are caused by beams of energetic electrons (tens to hundreds of keV) accelerated along open magnetic field lines during magnetic reconnection in solar flares. These electron beams excite Langmuir waves, which are converted into radio emissions at the local plasma frequency and its harmonic. Regarding their spectral characteristics, type III bursts show rapid drifts from high to low frequencies over timescales of seconds, as accelerated electrons propagate outwards from the Sun through regions of decreasing plasma density. Type III bursts are observed as narrow, bright streaks in dynamic spectra in a broad frequency range, spanning from 100 MHz in the lower corona to 10 kHz in the IP medium, while fine-structure may be also observed due to variations in electron dynamics and wave-particle interactions. In powerful solar eruptive events with consecutive magnetic reconnection episodes, type III bursts are common occurrences and are most often observed in groups of various sizes/durations. Type III bursts present solid evidence of accelerated electrons escaping into the interplanetary medium ([Reid & Vilmer 2017](#)).

2.2.1 Instruments:

In the present catalogue we have made use of solar radio observations from both ground-based and space borne observatories allowing us to cover type III radio bursts from the low corona to tens of solar

radii. Ground-based radio observatories can observe in the decimetre-to-meter wave band (frequencies 1 GHz – 100 MHz) range which correspond to typical coronal heights observed of 0.5 to 1 solar radii above the photosphere. We made use of ground-based observations in the frequency range 25-180 MHz and include the Learmonth solar observatory in Australia, Holloman AFB in New Mexico and Sagamore Hill Solar Observatory in Massachusetts, USA, the Palehua solar observatory in Hawaii, and San Vito solar observatory in Italy. Radio burst logs and dynamic spectra have been inspected as well, when available, from the Culgoora solar observatory in Australia (18-1800 MHz), Hiraiso observatory in Japan (25 MHz - 2.5 GHz), ARTEMIS IV radio spectrograph in Thermolytae, Greece (20-650 MHz), the Nancay Decametric Array (NDA, 10-120 MHz) and the ORFEES radio spectrograph (144-1004 MHz) in France.

We also performed a search of type III on data from space-borne instruments, namely WIND / Radio and Plasma Wave Investigation (WAVES) and Solar Terrestrial Relations Observatory (STEREO) / WAVES experiments. WIND/WAVES receivers RAD1 and RAD2 operate at 20 kHz–1.04 MHz and 1.075–13.825 MHz respectively, while the corresponding Low Frequency Receiver (LFR) and High Frequency Receiver (HFR) of the similar WAVES instrument onboard STEREO Ahead and Behind twin spacecraft operate at 2.6 -153 kHz and 125 kHz - 16.025 MHz respectively. Both WIND/WAVES and STEREO/WAVES data are provided at one minute resolution. Radio spectrographs at ground-based stations of the Radio Solar Telescope Network (RSTN) have also been exploited in the analysis. These observe at 25-180 MHz and include the Learmonth solar observatory in Australia, Holloman AFB in New Mexico and Sagamore Hill Solar Observatory in Massachusetts, USA, the Palehua solar observatory in Hawaii, and San Vito solar observatory in Italy. Radio burst logs and dynamic spectra have been inspected as well, when available, from the Culgoora solar observatory in Australia (18-1800 MHz), Hiraiso observatory in Japan (25 MHz - 2.5 GHz), ARTEMIS IV radio spectrograph in Thermolytae, Greece (20-650 MHz), the Nancay Decametric Array (NDA, 10-120 MHz) and the ORFEES radio spectrograph (144-1004 MHz) in France.

The reason to consider both types of instruments is to maximize the spectral and temporal coverage of the analysis. Space-borne instruments offer the advantages of continuous temporal coverage as they operate without atmospheric or diurnal constraints, while ground-based observations are limited to local daytime and clear weather conditions. Ground-based instruments typically detect radio emissions in the range of 10 MHz to a few GHz frequencies generated in the solar corona, while lower frequencies cannot be observed due to the ionospheric absorption cutoff at ~ 10 MHz. Space-borne instruments provide the capability to detect radio emissions at lower frequencies in the kHz to MHz range that originate in the outer corona and IP space. The combination of both sources enables the tracking of the corresponding travelling disturbances from dense regions of the lower corona to the sparse outer corona and all the way into IP space.

Especially in the case of available observations from different vantage points in space, the localization and dynamical reconstruction of the particle release process may be feasible. The joint exploitation of space-borne and ground-based radio burst observations therefore provides complementary information into particle acceleration and transport processes, from the early stages of an eruptive event in the corona to the propagation of particles into the IP space. The instruments considered in search of the radio signatures of SEP events in our catalog are summarized in Table 1 below, along with the corresponding frequency ranges and timespan of operations.

2.2.2 Methodology:

The search for type III radio signatures of SEP events in our catalog is based on the temporal association of such bursts with the timing of the parent solar eruption, in particular the start and peak time of the solar

Table 1: Space-borne and ground based instruments considered in the search for radio burst associations for SEP events in the >100 MeV protons catalog.

Ground-based instruments				
Station	Acronym	Frequency range (MHz)	Timespan	Location
Learmonth	LEAR	25-180	1975-present	Learmonth, Australia
San Vito	SVTO	25-180	1994-present	San Vito, Italy
Sagamore Hill	SGMR	25-180	1975-present	Massachusetts, USA
Potsdam	POTS	40-800	1993-2006	Potsdam, Germany
Holloman	HOLL	25-180	1996-present	New Mexico, USA
Palehua	PALE	25-180	1980-present	Hawaii, US
Culgoora	CULG	18-1800	1975-2019	New South Wales, Australia
HiRAS	HIRA	25-2500	1992-2016	Hiraiso, Japan
Izmiran	IZMI	20-260	1985-2016	Moscow, Russia
Nancay Decameter Array	NDA	10-120	1980-present	Nancay, France
ORFEES	ORFEES	144-1004	1975-present	Massachusetts, USA
ARTEMIS-IV	ARTEMIS	20-650	1998-2013	Thermopylae, Greece
Bleien	BLEN	100–1000	1979-2014	Aargau, Switzerland
Space-borne instruments				
Spacecraft	Instrument	Frequency range (MHz)	Timespan	Orbit
WIND	WAVES	0.02-13.8	1994-present	L1
STEREO A	WAVES	0.01-16.1	2006-present	Heliocentric \sim 1 AU
STEREO B	WAVES	0.01-16.1	2006-2014	Heliocentric \sim 1 AU

flare in SXR. Therefore, in cases where the parent solar flare is clearly identified, the corresponding radio bursts are retrieved in the timespan from \sim 10 minutes earlier than the start of the SXR flare up until 1 hour around the flare peak (for gradual SEP events).

The primary search for possible type III radio signatures of SEP events in the catalog has been performed on data from WIND / Radio and Plasma Wave Investigation (WAVES) and Solar Terrestrial Relations Observatory (STEREO) / WAVES experiments. Type III bursts in dynamic spectra of these instruments have been identified through visual inspection. An additional query for ground-based observations was carried out on data from the Radio Solar Telescope Network (RSTN) and several other solar radio observatories by means of compiled reports provided by NOAA¹ and SolarMonitor². Composite dy-

¹<https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/stp/space-weather/solar-data/solar-features/solar-radio/radio-bursts/reports/spectral-listings/>

²<https://www.solarmonitor.org/data/>

namic spectra of both space-borne and ground-based instruments, when available, have been retrieved from the Radio Monitoring³ service at LESIA (Observatoire de Paris).

The retrieved radio signatures have been cross-checked against other published catalogues. In particular, for type III identifications we refer to Papaioannou et al. (2016), spanning 1998-2013 and to the PhD thesis of Ath. Kouloumvakos in 2017 covering 1997-2010⁴. Common identifications in either of the referenced catalogues are included in the “Notes” column of type III information in our SEP event catalogue.

2.2.3 Encountered difficulties / limitations of the method:

The association with radio signatures is more difficult in cases where the parent solar eruption is unclear, that is mostly the case for events with no flare association and/or far-side events. For these cases, possible identified radio signatures of particle acceleration, in the timespan of a few hours before the SEP event onset, might help in the disentanglement of the parent solar event.

2.2.4 Data entries into the catalogue:

Type III radio signatures have been retrieved for almost all events in the catalogue: 167 out of 169 events (~99%) have been associated with type III bursts. For each successful type III association, we registered the start date/time of the type III, its frequency range of occurrence that are shown in Figure 4. Events for which an association could not be established because no data was available appeared as '/'.

SOHO/ERNE > 100 MeV §		Ground-based		Radio Type III		Spaceborne Observations		Notes
No	Identifier	Station	Start date	Start time		Start Date	Start Time	
80	20050907T123000	NO			WAVES	20050907	17:38	Ref AP2016
81	20060706T101000	LEAR, SVTO	20060706	08:17	WAVES	20060706	08:19	Ref AP2016, AKpHD
82	20061205T081500	SGMR	20061206	18:42	WAVES	20061206	18:40	Ref AP2016
83	20061213T025000	CULG, HIRA, PALE	20061213	02:24	SWAVES/WAVES	20061213	02:24	Ref AP2016, AKpHD
84	20061214T231000	CULG, HIRA	20061214	22:19	SWAVES/WAVES	20061214	22:00	Also GG at 22:10. Ref AP2016
85	20110128T031000	CULG, HIRA	20110128	00:57	SWAVES/WAVES	20110128	00:56	
86	20110307T122500	NO			SWAVES/WAVES	20110307	19:45	Ref AP2016
87	20110321T032500	CULG, LEAR	20110321	02:18	SWAVES/WAVES	20110321	02:16	Ref AP2016
88	20110605T145000	NO			SWAVES/WAVES	20110604	21:46	
89	20110607T065500	NO			SWAVES/WAVES	20110607	06:26	Ref AP2016
90	20110802T070500	NO			SWAVES/WAVES	20110802	06:03	
91	20110804T043000	CULG	20110804	03:50	SWAVES/WAVES	20110804	03:49	Ref AP2016
92	20110809T081000	NDA, ARTEMIS	20110809	08:02	SWAVES/WAVES	20110809	08:01	Ref AP2016
93	20110906T022000	CULG, LEAR	20110906	01:44	SWAVES/WAVES	20110906	01:44	Ref AP2016
94	20110906T233000	NO			SWAVES/WAVES	20110906	22:21	
95	20110922T141500	NDA	20110922	10:39	SWAVES/WAVES	20110922	10:39	Ref AP2016

Figure 7: Extract of the catalogue entries related to the type III radio bursts.

2.2.5 Future improvements:

This is the first round of iterations to uncover radio signatures for SEP events in our catalogue of >100 MeV proton events, and results will be revisited in the following years of the project through the following actions:

- **Inclusion of additional data:** The associations are expected to be refined and extended with the use of more instruments in the analysis, especially for the most recent events. Such instruments include the ground-based network e-Callisto⁵ and the Low Frequency Array (LOFAR)⁶, as well as

³<https://secchirh.obspm.fr/spip.php?article11>

⁴<https://www.didaktorika.gr/eadd/handle/10442/44779>

⁵<https://www.e-callisto.org/>

⁶<https://www.lofar.eu/>

the space-borne instruments onboard the Parker Solar Probe and Solar Orbiter missions.

2.2.6 Statistics of the association

Type III radio signatures have been retrieved for the majority of events in the catalogue: 167 out of 169 events ($\sim 99\%$) have been associated with type III bursts.

Figure 8: Distribution of the SEP events with respect to $\Delta t = t_{SEP} - t_{III}$. Events to the left of 00:00 had associated type III events that started prior to the time of the SEP onset, while events to the right of 00:00 had associated type III events that occurred after the SEP onset time

2.3 Identifications of CMEs:

CMEs are defined as sudden large-scale releases of plasma ejected into the upper corona and the solar wind. All CMEs result from the reconfiguration of coronal magnetic fields but they can form through a number of different processes. Strong CMEs tend to occur in association with other eruptive phenomena like solar flares or prominence eruptions (Yashiro et al. 2005). Fast and wide CMEs should be considered part of the broader phenomenon known as solar storms with different characteristic phases including (1) an initiation phase involving usually flaring/prominence activity, (2) an expansion in the corona with the potential formation of shock waves and generally strong disruptions of the solar atmosphere over a broad regions and (3) the eruptive/expulsion of mass and magnetic flux from the lower corona into the interplanetary medium. When the CME structure appears as a halo-like excess brightness surrounding the occulting disk in coronagraphs, it is named a halo CME (see Webb & Howard 2012, and references therein).

2.3.1 Methodology

The association with CMEs was made using the LASCO C2 and C3 coronagraphs onboard the SOLar and Heliospheric Observatory (SoHO). The two coronagraphs have provided continuous monitoring of the solar corona since 1996 (except between 25 June 1998 and mid-November 1998 when SoHO was temporarily lost). The analysis of imagery is highly time consuming and fortunately a catalogue of manually identified CMEs based on C2 and C3 observations now covers the January 1996 to August 2024 time period at the time of writing. More than 10 CMEs can occur on a single day, and many CMEs can appear at the same time in the C2 FOV. The Coronagraph Position Angle (CPA) is used in the LASCO

CME catalogue (Gopalswamy et al. 2009) to distinguish these CMEs appearing simultaneously. CMEs that exhibit an apparent width of 360° are marked as Halo in the CPA column.

Each CME in the LASCO CME catalogue is characterized by three speeds: (1) the linear speed obtained by fitting a straight line (aka linear or first-order polynomial fit) to the height-time measurements, (2) quadratic speed obtained by fitting a parabola (aka quadratic or second-order polynomial fit) to the height-time measurements and evaluating the speed at the time of final (last possible) height measurement, and (3) speed obtained as in (2) but evaluated when the CME is at a height of 20 solar radii. We used the linear speed estimates in the entries of our CME association catalogue.

For each SEP event we took into account the onset of the already identified and associated soft X-ray flare in section 2.1 and considered CMEs identified in the LASCO catalogue occurring after that onset. Since $>100\text{MeV}$ SEPs are powerful events, they are always associated with fast CMEs that stand out and are easily associated in the LASCO CME catalogue. There were times, however, of LASCO data outages that are flagged as such in the catalogue.

The CME information entered in of the catalogue (Figure 9) are the first time of imaging of the CME in the LASCO C2 coronagraph, the linear speed of the CME, the width of the CME expressed in terms of its extent in position angle and a weblink to a movie of the CME provided by the LASCO CME catalogue.

ID		CMEs			
No	Identifier	Date	Speed km/s	Width degree	Source
30	2001-09-15T13:10:00	11:54	478	130	SOHO/LASCO CME cat
31	2001-09-24T11:35:00	10:30	2402	halo	SOHO/LASCO CME cat
32	2001-10-01T13:25:00	05:30	1405	halo	SOHO/LASCO CME cat
33	2001-10-19T02:00:00	01:27	558	halo	SOHO/LASCO CME cat
34	2001-10-19T17:35:00	16:50	901	halo	SOHO/LASCO CME cat
35	2001-10-22T15:50:00	15:06	1336	halo	SOHO/LASCO CME cat
36	2001-11-04T16:40:00	16:35	1810	halo	SOHO/LASCO CME cat
37	2001-11-22T20:55:00	20:30	1443	halo	SOHO/LASCO CME cat
38	2001-11-28T22:45:00	17:30	500	halo	SOHO/LASCO CME cat
39	2001-12-26T05:40:00	05:30	1446	>212	SOHO/LASCO CME cat
40	2001-12-29T11:05:00	09:54	634	>150	SOHO/LASCO CME cat
41	2002-01-14T09:05:00	05:35	1492	halo	SOHO/LASCO CME cat
42	2002-01-27T13:30:00	12:30	1136	halo	SOHO/LASCO CME cat

Figure 9: Extract of the catalogue entries related to the LASCO CME associations.

2.3.2 Improvements

Future improvements of the catalogue would consider additional information provided by the SECCHI package onboard STEREO (Howard et al. 2008) which consists of an Extreme Ultraviolet Imager (EUVI), two coronagraphs (COR-1 and COR-2), and the Heliospheric Imager (HI) on each twin spacecraft. This will include a refined analysis of the CME properties provided by the integration of additional catalogues such as the CME deprojected speeds obtained from heliospheric imagery ⁷.

⁷https://www.helcats-fp7.eu/catalogues/wp3_cat.html

Figure 10: Statistics on the identified CMEs associated with the $>100\text{MeV}$ events (96%, 162/169 events). Panel on the left: distribution of the CME speeds in km/s. Panel on the right: distribution of the CME widths in deg.

Figure 11: Timing difference (hours in UT) between SEP event onset determined with SOHO/ERNE and CME start determined with SOHO/LASCO.

2.3.3 First Results

Figure 10 presents some interesting initial results based on the association work between the $>100\text{MeV}$ catalogue and CME events. We show the speeds and widths of the identified CMEs associated with SEP events (96%, 162/169 events). The unidentified sources are due to data gaps in SOHO/LASCO. CMEs speeds are comprised between 448 and 3387 km/s, with a median of 1336 km/s and a mean of 1404 km/s. Their minimum width is 76° and their maximum is 360° , corresponding to halo CMEs. The mean of their widths is 331° whereas their median is 360° . Such results point to the fact that strong SEP events are mostly associated with fast, halo CMEs (see e.g. Papaioannou et al. 2016, and references therein). Figure 11 presents the statistics on the delay between the $>100\text{MeV}$ proton onset (from SOHO/ERNE) and the CME start time (from SOHO/LASCO images). Similar to Figure 6, we removed the 10 August 2001, 5 December 2006 and 12 October 2013 events.

2.4 Identification of type II radio bursts

Type II radio bursts, of interest here, are the signatures of particles accelerated by shock waves passing through the solar atmosphere and usually driven by the expansion and outflow of fast CMEs (Kumari et al. 2023, and references therein). As such Type II radio bursts provide evidence of coronal shock waves which are considered as efficient particle accelerators. Shock waves are strong contenders for the origin of very high energy SEPs (Klein 2021b). Type II bursts are observed in dynamic radio spectra as slowly drifting and often intermittent narrowband radio emission. The morphological characteristics of the Type II burst depend on the shock wave properties and the upstream plasma conditions (Wild et al. 1963).

2.4.1 Instruments

In the present catalogue we have made use of the same solar radio observations as for the type III radio burst identification, i.e. from both ground-based and space borne observatories, allowing us to cover type II radio bursts from the low corona to tens of solar radii

2.4.2 Methodology

Identification of Type II bursts requires a visual inspection of spectrograms, as type IIs often occur in close temporal proximity with other radio bursts such as Type III and Type IV, albeit at slightly different times and frequencies. A classic sequence of events in radio spectrograms from ground-based observatories is the first occurrence of a rapidly drifting Type III burst (triggered by the flare electrons), followed immediately by the more slowly drifting Type II emission (triggered locally in the shock vicinity). The separation between Type II and Type III bursts at the lower frequencies measured by spacecraft is usually much clearer, because the flare electrons propagate much faster than the shock and are therefore at very different radial distances by the time they are detected in space-based spectrograms.

ID		Radio Type II								
No	Identifier	Ground-based observations				Spaceborne Observations				
		Station	Start date	Start time	Freq range (MHz)	Date	Time	Freq range (kHz)		
50	20020822T022000	PALE, CULG, HIRA, LEAR	20020822	01:55	200-25	WAVES	20020822	02:50	14000-3500	
51	20020824T012000	PALE, LEAR, CULG, HOLL, HIRA	20020824	01:01	190-25	WAVES	20020824	01:45	5000-400	
52	20021219T230500	CULG, PALE, HOLL	20021219	21:39	180-25	WAVES	20021219	21:45	14000-1500	
53	20030423T013500	CULG	20030423	01:01	300-27	NO	NO	NO	NO	
54	20030528T033500	PALE	20030528	00:26	180-25	WAVES	20030528	01:00	1000-200	
55	20030531T025000	PALE, CULG, LEAR	20030531	02:20	180-25	WAVES	20030531	03:00	1000-150	
56	20031026T174500	CULG, HIRA, LEAR	20031026	06:16	330-25	WAVES	20031026	07:00	8000-1500	
57	20031028T112000	BLEN, SGMR, SVTO	20031028	11:00	1400-25	WAVES	20031028	11:10	14000-40	
58	20031029T210500	CULG, HOLL, PALE, SGMR	20031029	20:40	1000-25	WAVES	20031029	20:55	11000-500	
59	20031102T173000	HOLL, PALE	20031102	17:14	180-25	WAVES	20031102	17:30	12000-250	
60	20031104T215000	CULG, HOLL, PALE, SGMR	20031104	19:42	180-20	WAVES	20031104	20:00	10000-200	
61	20031120T083000	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	
62	20040723T093000	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	
63	20040725T184500	SVTO	20040725	15:21	25-81	WAVES	20040725	15:00	1000-28	
64	20040919T144000	PALE, SGMR	20040919	16:55	180-25	WAVES	20040919	17:15	14000-2500	
65	20041101T061000	CULG, PALE, HIRA, LEAR	20041101	03:21	250-25	WAVES	20041101	05:55	3000-400	
66	20041107T173000	SGMR	20041107	15:59	180-25	WAVES	20041107	16:25	14000-60	
67	20041109T185000	PALE, IZMI	20041109	17:18	56-25	WAVES	20041109	17:35	14000-5000	
68	20041110T023500	CULG, LEAR, HIRA	20041110	02:07	260-18	WAVES	20041110	02:25	14000-1000	
69	20050115T070000	CULG, LEAR, HIRA	20050115	05:55	140-18	WAVES	20050115	06:15	14000-250	
70	20050116T002000	HIRA, CULG, PALE, LEAR	20050115	22:24	410-18	WAVES	20050115	23:00	3000-40	
71	20050117T115500	SVTO, LEAR	20050117	09:43	70-25	WAVES	20050117	10:00	14000-4000	
72	20050120T0963500	CULG, LEAR, SVTO	20050120	06:44	180-18	WAVES	20050120	07:15	14000-25	
73	20050513T195000	POTS, SVTO, SGMR	20050513	16:38	350-25	WAVES	20050513	17:00	5000-40	
74	20050616T203500	PALE, SGMR, HIRA	20050616	20:10	180-25	WAVES	20050616	20:25	9000-1000	

Figure 12: Extract of the catalogue entries related to the type II radio bursts.

To achieve as complete time coverage as possible several ground-based observatories were considered. Indeed a CME is easily missed in ground-based radio observations as the type II will only be observed for several tens of minutes in metric and decametric radio spectrograms on top of that, an observatory needs to be on the dayside close to the onset time of the CME.

To build the type II catalogue, we considered the release times of the CMEs inferred from the CME and flare associations presented in the previous sections. Each ground-based spectrogram was then analysed carefully and when a slowly drifting type II emission was observed we recorded its start date/time and the frequency range over which the emission was observed.

The time of the lowest frequency emission from the ground-based spectrograms was then used to search for the presence of a type II burst in the lower frequency spectrograms recorded by space-borne instruments.

2.4.3 Data entries into the catalogue

For each successful type II association, we registered the start date/time of the type II and its frequency range of occurrence that are shown in Figure 4. Events for which an association could not be established because no data was available appeared as '/'.

The retrieved radio signatures have been cross-checked against other published catalogues. In particular, for type II bursts we refer to the catalog by [Gopalswamy et al. \(2019\)](#) which covers the years 1997-2023 (June). We also refer to [Papaioannou et al. \(2016\)](#) spanning 1998-2013 and to the PhD thesis of Ath. Kouloumvakos in 2017 covering events in 1997-2010. Common identifications in either of the three referenced catalogues are included in the “Notes” column of type II information in our [SEP](#) event catalog.

2.4.4 Statistics of the association

Type II radio signatures have been retrieved for the majority of events in the catalog: 155 out of 169 events ($\sim 92\%$) have been associated with type II bursts.

Figure 13: Distribution of the SEP events with respect to $\Delta t = t_{SEP} - t_{II}$. Events to the left of 0 had associated type II events that started prior to the time of the SEP onset, while events to the right of 0 had associated type II events that occurred after the SEP onset time

2.4.5 Future improvements

This is the first round of iterations to uncover type II signatures for [SEP](#) events in our catalog of >100 MeV proton events and results will be revisited in the following years of the project.

- **Exploitation of complementary ground-based facilities:** The associations are expected to be refined and extended with the use of more instruments in the analysis, especially for the most recent events. Such instruments include the ground-based network e-Callisto⁸ and the Low Frequency Array (LOFAR)⁹, as well as the space-borne instruments onboard the Parker Solar Probe and Solar Orbiter missions.
- **Multi-vantage point observations:** Recently published catalogues such as the multi-vantage point observations of type II bursts¹⁰ by ([Mohan et al. 2024](#)) could be exploited to provide additional information on the type II bursts.

⁸<https://www.e-callisto.org/>

⁹<https://www.lofar.eu/>

¹⁰https://cdaw.gsfc.nasa.gov/CME_list/radio/multimission_type2/Full_catalog.html

- **Shock speeds from radio spectrograms:** The frequency drift of type II radio bursts can be exploited in conjunction with density models of the solar corona and interplanetary medium to infer the speed of shock waves. A review of past radio burst studies and known databases¹¹ would be carried out to include these shock speeds in our catalogue.

2.5 Identifications of hard X-ray signatures:

While the radiation observed at soft X-ray energies considered in section 2.1 is typically from a thermal plasma with a temperature in the order of 10-30 MK, the hard X-ray spectrum is dominated by bremsstrahlung from the accelerated electrons and, at the lower hard X-ray energies, by thermal bremsstrahlung from plasma at temperatures above about 30 MK. Hard X-ray observations allow us to study the accelerated electrons and the hottest plasma in flares. Bremsstrahlung emission occurs when the energetic electrons accelerated in the solar flare are suddenly decelerated by interactions with the thermal protons of the solar atmosphere. The strongest particle acceleration occurs during the impulsive phase and is most obviously characterised by impulsive hard X-ray (HXR) and microwave emission both implying the presence of the non-thermal electrons (see e.g. Klein 2021a).

2.5.1 Instruments

The hard X-ray flare association was carried out by considering data from the the Reuven Ramaty High Energy Solar Spectroscopic Imager (RHESSI; Lin et al. 2002) in the energy range of 3 keV-20 MeV. Reuven Ramaty High Energy Solar Spectroscopic Imager (RHESSI) was a NASA spacecraft dedicated to observing solar flares in hard X-rays and γ -rays, it was launched in February 2002 in a Low-Earth Orbit (LEO). After more than 16 years of successful operation, RHESSI was decommissioned on August 2018. The Spectrometer Telescope for Imaging X-rays Spectrometer Telescope for Imaging X-rays of Solar Orbiter (STIX) on Solar Orbiter was operational soon after the launch of the mission on 10 February 2020. STIX is a hard X-ray imaging spectrometer covering the energy range from 4 to 150 keV.

We used the RHESSI data to analyse hard X-ray signature of events 52 to 135 and the Solar Orbiter STIX data to analyse events 136 to 169. We analysed the time series of the RHESSI data available online at the RHESSI data browser and the STIX data available on the STIX data browser¹² We have also made use of the RHESSI¹³ and the STIX¹⁴ flare catalogues.

2.5.2 Methodology

In order to connect a >100 MeV SEP event with the HXR measurements, we consider the onset of the hard X-ray emission and compared it to the onset of the soft X-ray flare already associated with the SEP event in section 2.1. If the onset of the hard X-ray flare occurs before the onset of the soft X-ray emission we consider they are not associated since hard X-ray emission always occurs in conjunction with the soft X-rays. Similarly if the onset of the hard X-rays occurs more than 30 minutes after the soft X-ray flare it is also not considered associated.

¹¹<https://www.sws.bom.gov.au/Solar/4/3>

¹²<https://datacenter.stix.i4ds.net/view/plot/lightcurves#>

¹³https://hesperia.gsfc.nasa.gov/hessidata/dbase/hessi_flare_list.txt

¹⁴<https://datacenter.stix.i4ds.net/view/flares/list>

ID		hard X-rays
		Instrument
No	Identifier	
134	2017-09-08T19:25:00	RHESSI
135	2017-09-10T03:45:00	RHESSI
136	2021-05-28T23:40:00	No STIX
137	2021-10-28T16:05:00	STIX HXR
138	2022-01-20T06:15:00	STIX HXR
139	2022-02-16T05:15:00	No data
140	2022-03-14T20:15:00	STIX HXR
141	2022-03-21T06:10:00	STIX HXR

Figure 14: Extract of the catalogue entries related to the hard X-ray flare associations.

2.5.3 Encountered difficulties

The **RHESSI** and **STIX** instruments offer only a limited view of the hard X-ray emission since they operated over different time periods and they are mostly sensitive to hard X-rays produced by particles interacting with the visible disk of which only half the surface can of course be observed at any one time. For flares occurring just behind the limb the hard X-ray monitors will record the coronal component of the hard X-ray emission only. Consequently **RHESSI** measures only a fraction or even no emission produced in occulted flares viewed from Earth's perspective. Since the $>100\text{MeV}$ SEP list was built from in situ measurements of energetic particles taken in the near-Earth environment, the **STIX** data can often miss or only partially measure the hard X-rays of the relevant flare.

2.5.4 Future improvements

The associations made so far in the catalogue are preliminary and will require further verifications. Additional aspects that should be considered in future versions of the catalogue such as:

- **RHESSI** and **STIX** provide the onset time, duration and peak flux of the hard X-ray flares which should be integrated in the catalogue.
- In a future revision of the catalogue, the hard X-ray flare positions derived by **RHESSI** and **STIX** could be compared to the positions of the solar flares provided in section 2.1 and also added to the catalogue.

2.6 Identifications of γ -rays:

Observations of γ -rays and neutrons during flares provide the only information on the properties of very energetic ions accelerated in the corona and impacting the lower solar atmosphere (Vilmer et al. 2011). Energetic ions interacting with the solar atmosphere produce an abundance of γ -ray emissions. A γ -ray line spectrum is produced by interactions of ions in the range 1-100 MeV/nucleon and consists of several nuclear de-excitation lines, neutron capture lines and positron annihilation lines. In the presence of more energetic ions, above a few hundred MeV/nucleon, nuclear interactions with the surrounding medium produce secondary pions whose decay products give rise to a broadband continuum detectable at photon energies above 10 MeV. The pion decay emission below the peak of 70 MeV γ -rays is dominated by both bremsstrahlung and the annihilation in flight of positrons from positive pion decays. At energies >100 MeV, the emission is dominated by neutral pion decay.

The γ -ray emission often appears to occur during two phases which were first reported by Frost & Dennis (1971). The first emission occurs during the solar flare and has been related to particle acceler-

ation within the reconnection process occurring within the flare. The second stage is significantly harder, and it has been suggested that it may instead originate from particles accelerated by the CME shock and could therefore be associated with powerful SEPs. Before Fermi, only two long-lived (hours long) γ -ray emissions were observed by EGRET (e.g. [Kanbach et al. 1994](#); [Ryan 2000](#)).

With the advent of the Fermi-Large Area Telescope instrument in 2008 (The Fermi Large Area Telescope (LAT); [Atwood et al. 2009](#)), these sustained emissions or second stage acceleration events have been detected during many energetic solar flares ([Ackermann et al. 2014](#); [Share et al. 2018](#)). The durations of the sustained γ -rays were shown to correlate with the durations of the associated > 100 MeV solar energetic proton events, but the SEP durations tend to be five times longer ([Share et al. 2018](#)). The associated >100 MeV proton events typically last no longer than 1 day. Although there appears to be an association with SEPs, sustained emissions are not always detected in conjunction with >100 MeV SEP event, this result is confirmed below with our >100 MeV SEP catalogue.

When solar flares erupt beyond the visible disk of the Sun and behind the limbs γ -rays can on occasions be recorded by Fermi-LAT ([Ackermann et al. 2017](#)) indicating that sustained γ -ray emission can extend up to tens of degrees from the location of the active region ([Plotnikov et al. 2017](#)). The onset of sustained γ -ray emissions is consistent with the timing of the CME, when high-Mach number CME shocks first intersect with magnetic field lines returning to the Sun ([Plotnikov et al. 2017](#)).

Considering these past studies, it is clearly highly desirable to know if a particular >100 MeV proton event measured in situ occurs in conjunction with >100 MeV γ -ray events induced when >300 MeV protons induce pion decay in the low solar atmosphere.

2.6.1 Instruments:

The main source of γ -ray measurements since 2009 has been the LAT instrument ([Atwood et al. 2009](#)) which is sensitive to γ -rays in the energy range between 30 MeV and >300 GeV ([Lange & Pohl 2013](#)). With its effective field of view of 2.4 steradians, the instrument can observe 20% of the sky at any given time, and scan the entire sky in three hours (until 2016). Its angular resolution, which is 5° for 100 MeV γ -rays and becomes more precise for more energetic rays, reaching 6 arcminutes at 10 GeV. Its sensitivity is almost 20 times greater than that of the EGRET instrument on the Compton Gamma-Ray Observatory that discovered solar gamma ray flares.

The instrument records energy, direction and time information for each detected particle. Each such "event" is classified by ground processing as a photon or other particle, based on the consistency of its interaction with that expected from energetic γ -rays. Fermi LAT is so sensitive that it observes quiescent solar emission on a near daily basis that originates from cosmic-ray proton collisions in the photosphere (producing pion-decay radiation) and from Compton up-scattering of solar blackbody photons by cosmic-ray electrons. Background in public data almost entirely due to galactic and extragalactic point sources and diffuse components.

In the present analysis, we use the publicly available LAT data. Since Fermi was launched in 2009, the search for the presence of γ -ray events during our >100 MeV SEP catalogue could only be carried out for events 85 to 169 that occurred between 2011 and 2024.

2.6.2 Methodology:

The association between the > 100 MeV proton catalogue and the γ -ray catalogue was done manually via a direct inspection of the γ ray time series. We make use of two methods for analyzing the LAT data

Figure 15: Example of a Fermi LAT curve computed using the simple Light-Bucket accumulation of photons within a 10° circle of the Sun for the well-known 2017 September 10 long duration γ -ray event.

known as the a “light bucket” (LB) and “maximum likelihood” (ML) method. The light bucket is less sophisticated but faster than the maximum likelihood approach used by [Ackermann et al. \(2014\)](#) and [Ajello et al. \(2014\)](#), but it is almost as sensitive for detecting long-duration high-energy solar γ -ray events. With this approach, the γ -ray background is reduced from the atmosphere of the Earth by restricting the allowable events to those with zenith angles $< 100^\circ$ and only considered γ -rays with energies > 100 MeV. With these restrictions all photons with measured locations within about 10° of the Sun are considered thus basically forming a ‘light bucket’. About 95% of all 200 MeV solar γ -rays have measured locations within this 10° region of interest.

In the ML Method, the likelihood L is the probability of obtaining the data given an input model. The input model is the distribution of γ -ray sources on the sky, and includes their intensity and spectra. There is an implicit assumption that we understand sufficiently well the response of our detectors, in this case the LAT, to the incident flux, in other words, that we have a sufficiently accurate mapping of the input model (the γ -ray sky) to the data (the list of counts produced by either the LAT or the The Fermi Gamma-ray Burst Monitor (GBM)). An example of a > 100 MeV γ -ray time series derived with the LB method is given in Figure 15 for the event of 2017 September 10. The red points highlight values of γ -ray fluxes that are significantly higher than the background and can be considered a solar γ -ray event. In addition to the analysis of time series, we have also made use of the Fermi LAT Significant Event List¹⁵ which provides the time periods with LAT fluxes greater than 4.2 sigma above the mean flux.

2.6.3 Data entries into the catalogue:

In this first version of the catalogue, we consider an association between a γ -ray event and an > 100 MeV SEP event when a γ -ray event occurred during or within 12 hours of the onset of the SEP event. These entries are shown in Figure 4 and at this stage are limited to simply declaring the occurrence of a significant increase in > 100 MeV γ -ray flux either by the LB or the ML method.

¹⁵https://hesperia.gsfc.nasa.gov/fermi/lat/qlook/lat_events.txt

SOHO/ERNE > 100 MeV SEP		
ID		Gamma Rays
No	Identifier	Instrument
157	20240129T044000	NO
158	20240209T143000	LAT (LB / ML)
159	20240211T004000	NO
160	20240212T071000	NO
161	20240216T073000	LAT (LB / ML)
162	20240323T025000	NO DATA
163	20240511T015000	NO DATA
164	20240513T170000	NO DATA
165	20240520T103500	NO
166	20240607T235000	NO
167	20240611T222000	NO DATA
168	20240723T004000	NO
169	20240805T143500	NO DATA

Figure 16: Extract of the catalogue entries related to the γ -ray associations.

2.6.4 Statistics of the association

Of the 165 $>100\text{MeV}$ SEP events that occurred during the Fermi mission, we found 24 associated γ -ray events, i.e. 14% of the events. There are multiple reasons for this low number.

- First, it should be noted that in order to induce pion production and decay, protons must interact with the low solar atmosphere with energies greater than 300 MeV and not 100 MeV. The subset of SEP events associated with GLE or sub-GLE events were all related to a γ -ray event except for one when Fermi-LAT was not acquiring data. It would be interesting to isolate the SEP events of the > 100 MeV SEP catalogue for which higher energies were definitely measured from other SEP measurements.
- Second, Fermi-LAT observes the Sun only a fraction of the time due to its inclined low-Earth orbit. It is therefore likely that short duration γ -ray flares were missed for some SEP events because Fermi was on the night-side of the Earth ("Fermi night").
- Third, some $>100\text{MeV}$ SEPs originate from far-side events that are not well connected magnetically to the visible disk and therefore not associated with γ -rays.

2.6.5 Future Improvements:

Future improvements of the catalogue could include:

- estimates of the start and end times of the γ ray events, although this is not always feasible because events are often only partially observed by Fermi LAT due to Fermi's orbit. We could, for instance, specify whether the γ -ray event was associated with sustained emission or not. The catalogue could also include information on the measured peak γ -ray flux.

2.7 Association of Shock Modelling:

The work reported in this section is in anticipation to deliverable D4.3 which will be dedicated to shock modelling.

When CMEs travel outward from the Sun, they undergo significant expansion due to the decreasing pressure of the surrounding solar wind. This expansion occurs both laterally and radially, causing the CME to grow in size and potentially impact a broader area. When the CME speed exceeds that of the ambient solar wind, it compresses the plasma ahead of it, forming a pressure wave. As particles encounter a propagating coronal shock, they may experience significant acceleration and reach high energies through a number of processes.

The outermost surface of CMEs where pressure waves form that potentially steepen into shock waves have been shown to follow an ellipsoid geometry (Jarry et al. 2023). By fitting the CME outermost boundary on successive images and from several vantage points simultaneously, the position and dimensions of the ellipsoid can be determined. Such shock wave 3D reconstructions offer a lot of advantages, such as going beyond the projection effects to track its height and speed in the corona more accurately and in 3D.

2.7.1 Methodology

We first considered the CME association already carried out in section 2.3. We then used the technique developed in Rouillard et al. (2016) which consists in fitting shock waves in 3-D using multipoint imagery (see previous section) to derive the velocity field of each point on the expanding pressure wave/shock. All available spacecraft imagery (Solar-Terrestrial Relations Observatory (STEREO) Extrem Ultraviolet Imager on Solar Orbiter (EUI)/COR1/COR2/HI1/2), SOHO C2/C3, Solar Dynamics Observatory (SDO) The Atmospheric Imaging Assembly (AIA), Parker Solar Probe (PSP) Wide Imager of (WISPR) and Solar Orbiter EUI/METIS/HI) is typically considered for these detailed analysis. In order to obtain additional fundamental parameters of the shock, the technique also employs 3-D magneto-hydrodynamic (MagnetoHydroDynamic (MHD)) simulations Rouillard et al. (2016). The catalogue of Kouloumvakos et al. (2019) already includes 33 fitted shock waves, and we added 2 new fitted shocks during the first year of the SPEARHEAD project. These events are described in the next section that presents more in depth analysis of recent $> 100\text{MeV}$ SEP events and their solar associations.

Currently the only information entered in the catalogue is whether a fitted shock is available or not.

2.7.2 Improvements

The improvements will be carried out as part of deliverable D4.3 where parameters derived by the shock fittings will be integrated in the catalogue.

2.8 First Release of the solar association part of the Catalog

The $>100\text{ MeV}$ SEP catalogue is described in D5.1. That report, further includes a link that provides direct access to the catalogue. Here we discuss the solar association part of the catalogue, which is structured as follows:

- Columns N to T: X-rays flare information
 - Columns N and O: Date and time of onset (in UT)
 - Columns P and Q: Date and time of peak flux (in UT)
 - Column R: soft X-ray class (1–8 Å soft X-ray peak intensity in terms of C, M and X nomenclature where these represent intensities of 10^{-6} , 10^{-5} , and 10^{-4} W/m^2 respectively)
 - Column S: X-ray location on the solar surface (in Stonyhurst heliographic coordinates, degrees North (N) or South (S), and East (E) or West (W))

- Column T: Spacecraft observer
- Column U: hard X-ray flare instrument of observation (if any)
- Columns V to AB: Radio type III information
 - Column V: Ground-based station
 - Columns W and X: Start date and time of radio type III measured on ground (in UT)
 - Column Y: Spacecraft/Instrument
 - Columns ZZ and AA: Start date and time of radio type III measured on board (in UT)
 - Column AB: Notes on radio type III
- Columns AC to AK: Radio type II information
 - Columns AC to AD: Ground-based information
 - * Column AC: Station
 - * Columns AD and AE: Start date and time of radio type II measured on ground (in UT)
 - * Column AF: Frequency range [MHz]
 - Columns AG to AJ: On board information
 - * Column AG: Spacecraft/Instrument
 - * Columns AH and AI: Start date and time of radio type II measured on board (in UT)
 - * Column AJ: Frequency range [kHz]
 - Column AK: Notes on radio type II
- Columns AL: Gamma-rays information
- Columns AM to AP: CME information
 - Column AM: Start date of the CME (in UT)
 - Column AN: Linear speed of the CME [km/s]
 - Column AO: Angular width of the CME [deg]
 - Column AP: Source of information
- Column AQ: Ground Level Enhancement (GLE) number (if any)
- Column AR: Shock reconstruction information
- Column AS: Notes

3 In-depth analyses of the priority events

We have carried out a more in-depth analysis of the priority events defined in (Rouillard et al. 2024, hereafter D4.1). These in-depth and careful analysis are time consuming and only events deemed key for tackling the fundamental question of the origin of the highest SEPs, i.e. strategic for the SPEARHEAD project and its visibility, are considered.

During the first year of the project, we focused our attention on the most recent events of 2024 namely the 10-11 May and 8 June 2024. The reasons to focus on these events were that significant data is available from SDO, STEREO, SOHO, PSP, Fermi, Solar Orbiter, Bepi Colombo as well as a broad range of ground-based observatories. They offer unprecedented opportunities to study the origin of high-energy radiation in a comprehensive manner, folding in not only the properties of SEPs in situ (spatio-temporal, spectral, composition) but also their solar signatures. *The study presented in this section is currently being written up as an article to be submitted during the first semester of 2025.*

Figure 17: Image from Solar-MACH tool (Gieseler et al. 2023). Top view of the ecliptic plane from the North on the 11 May 2024. Red, green, yellow, purple and blue lines corresponds respectively to magnetic field lines connected to STEREO-A, the Earth, BepiColombo, PSP, SO.

3.1 10-11 May 2024 Event

3.1.1 The radiation storm

The 10-13 May 2024 solar storms led to the most powerful geomagnetic storm since March 1989 and produced auroras at low latitudes in both the northern and southern hemispheres. In deliverable D4.1, we assigned this May event priority order 2 (after the 8 June 2024 discussed in the next section which had priority order 1). The work reported here was presented during the European Space Weather Week (ESWW) 2024 in Coïmbra.

The orbital configuration (Figure 17) of spacecraft was favourable to measure the CMEs and the associated SEPs from several spacecraft i.e. from near-Earth, STEREO-A (STA) and Parker Solar Probe.

Figure 18 provides a summary of the radiation environment measured near-Earth and at STEREO-A. The geomagnetic storm started when a strong shock and complex solar ejecta hit the Earth's magnetosphere on 10th May 2024. The arrival of the strong shock drove a first minor radiation storm seen in the lower energy bands of GOES (Figure 18b), ERNE (Figure 18c) and HET (Figure 18d) peaking around the shock impact time.

Upon the arrival of the CMEs at Earth, ground-based neutron monitors around the globe also recorded a strong Forbush decrease (Papaioannou et al. 2020) in response to the shielding effects of these CMEs on the galactic cosmic rays (Figure 18a). As the cosmic ray flux reached a minimum on May 11 at 01:00 UT, a GLE was suddenly detected between 01:30 and 02:00 UT together with a powerful SEP event measured at the Lagrange L1 point and the STEREO-A (Figure 18bcd). The GLE has the official number 74 and the ground-based neutron monitor data are collected at the International GLE Database¹⁶.

We analysed the solar counterparts of this complex sequence of events including the state of the interplanetary medium during this powerful radiation storm and the properties of the measured GLE. We give a timing analysis of the in-situ particle recordings at L1. We then show modelling results of the

¹⁶<https://gle.oulu.fi/>

Figure 18: The radiation storm measured at Earth by OULU/SOPB NM (a) and in near-Earth by GOES (b), SoHO ERNE (c), STA HET (d). Solar wind speed measurements by STA and ACE (e) and a pitch angle spectrogram by STA SWEA. NM GLE onset (01:45 UT) and STA SEP onset (02:26 UT) are indicated.

coronal and interplanetary medium leading to this GLE.

3.1.2 The solar flare and the CME-driven shock wave

The SEP event followed a week of high solar activity driven by two large active region complexes AR13663 and AR1664. GOES detected a X5.8 flare onset at 01:11 UT with a peak measured at 01:22 UT from the complex of ARs situated at around S19W52. The peak of the flare occurs around the estimated SPR time of >100 MeV protons. A CME formed during the solar flare entering SoHO LASCO at 01:36UT and propagating with a speed of 1614 km/s (linear speed).

Figure 19: Summary of EUV and coronagraphic observations of the forming and expanding CME at different times (left column). Results of fitting the shock structure using the ellipsoidal model (right column).

An expanding bubble was clearly visible around the flaring site by 01:20 UT (top left panel of 19) and expanding into the coronagraph images middle and bottom panel). The expansion of this structure could be fitted in 3-D using the shock-fitting technique of Rouillard et al. (2016). The results of this fitting are superposed on the STEREO images in the right-hand panels of Figure 19. As we only had one point of view for the start of the event, we assumed a spherical shock and a perfectly radial propagation by using the statistical result of Jarry et al. (2023). This fitting technique provides the shock location and expansion speed over the entire expanding surface.

To obtain additional shock parameters we must use models of the background solar corona for that particular time of eruption (Rouillard et al. 2016). This can be achieved by exploiting 3-D magnetohy-

drodynamic (MHD) models of the solar atmosphere that use solar magnetograms as the inner boundary condition. For that we employ the global MHD simulation of the background corona provided by Predictive Sciences Inc called MAST¹⁷. Following the technique of Rouillard et al. (2016); Kouloumvakos et al. (2019), we then derive the 3-D distribution of the Mach number, shock geometry and shock geometry on the entire shock surface (23).

Figure 20: The reconstructed 3D shock wave and magnetic field lines connected to different spacecrafts, with the same colour code. The shock surface is coloured according to the intensity of the Alfvénic Mach number.

The result of this shock reconstruction reveals that a shock formed very early on, during the rising phase of X-ray flare between 01:11 UT and 01:15 UT. As seen in Figure 23, a strong shock formed during the solar flare with Alfvén Mach numbers in excess of 10. The flare and powerful shock, two possible accelerators of these particles, thus occurred in conjunction.

In order to determine whether the shock was magnetically connected to specific points of SEP measurements, we exploit a combination of the background MHD coronal model and an interplanetary magnetic field model to trace field lines backwards from the probe to the photosphere. For the analysis we assumed a Parker spiral for the background interplanetary magnetic field to establish magnetic connectivity. We then extract shock parameters along that field line as a function of time.

We found that around the solar particle release time, the Earth was connected magnetically to a quasi-perpendicular supercritical shock (>1600 km/s, $\text{Mach} > 3$, $\theta_{BN} > 60$). These shock conditions which are highly favourable for the acceleration of solar particles to high energy through the process of diffusive shock acceleration (Afanasiev et al. 2018). STEREO-A connected ten minutes later than Earth to a strong shock. As shown in Figure 18, near-Earth spacecraft and STEREO-A measured a powerful SEP event with Earth measuring the first energetic particles slightly early than Earth. All other probes were connected later to a much weaker part of the shock and measured much weaker SEPs. A next step in the analysis will be to quantify the acceleration process of energetic particles from the shock properties modelled here following a similar approach to that carried out in Afanasiev et al. (2018).

¹⁷https://www.predsci.com/mhdweb/summary_plots.php

Figure 21: Evolution of derived shock parameters along magnetic field lines from STEREO-A (red), Earth (green), PSP (purple), BepiColombo (yellow), and SO (blue) as a function of time. Left panels: from top to bottom, shock speed V_{sh} , Mach Alfvénic number M_A , Hoffman-Teller speed V_{HT} , Alfvén speed V_a . Right panels: from top to bottom, magnetic field obliquity θ_{BN} , Magnetosonic Mach number M_{MS} , compression ratio X_R , sound speed V_S .

3.1.3 The complex interplanetary conditions

The Parker spiral employed for the background interplanetary magnetic field to establish magnetic connectivity can be questioned for the present event. As often seen in past GLE events (Rouillard et al. 2016), the interplanetary magnetic field for GLE74 is highly disturbed by the presence of CMEs that erupted the days preceding the GLE. A careful analysis of the interplanetary plasma and magnetic field data taken at L1 and STEREO-A, plotted in Figure 22, reveals that the May superstorm was associated with the passage of five consecutive magnetic clouds labeled M1 to M5. These magnetic clouds are related to the eruption of five CMEs from May 8 to 10. We also identified three interplanetary shocks propagating within these magnetic clouds that could have been involved in potentially further acceleration of the SEPs. The leading shock S1 was particularly strong ($MA > 9$, see table below) and associated with an ESP event which could have acted as potentially pre-energised particles to produce GLE74.

Fig 22 shows that GLE74 occurred inside the trailing edge of the second magnetic cloud (M2) and before the following cloud (M3), consequently it is desirable to model the transport of SEPs inside a twisted magnetic flux rope instead of a simple Parker spiral.

3.1.4 Conclusions on the analysis of GLE74

We have shown that in conjunction with the X5.8 flare a very strong quasi-perpendicular shock formed near the estimated onset release time of SEPs. We have also found that the interplanetary conditions were highly disturbed during this event and that the SEPs propagated inside a magnetic flux rope. Future

Figure 22: Solar wind conditions before, during and after GLE 74. From top to bottom: the background total magnetic field and rms, the B_z component, elevation (theta) and azimuthal (phi) components of the magnetic field, the cosmic ray count rate from South Pole neutron monitor. Identified magnetic clouds are shown in color and labelled M1 to M5. *Credit: work carried out in collaboration with the Geosphere CME team in Graz, Austria.*

work will aim to model this SEP using as input the shock parameters derived from coronal modelling and we will also model the transport of SEPs in the complex interplanetary magnetic field of the preceding CMEs. This can be carried out by simulating the propagation of the 3D Eruptive Flux Rope model of Rouillard et al. (2020b) into IRAP's 3-D MHD interplanetary solar wind model, HELIOCAST (Réville et al. 2023) and then simulating the transport of SEPs through this complex interplanetary magnetic field. This is a common goal of the analysis of this GLE74 and GLE72 (also a priority event), both events for which the SEPs propagated through magnetic clouds to impact the Earth environment and produce the GLEs. This work will provide a better understanding of the effect of complex interplanetary magnetic fields on the transport of high-energy particles, an important goal of the SPEARHEAD project.

3.2 8 June 2024 Event

We now present a preliminary analysis of the 8 June 2024 SEP event (Event 166 of the >100 MeV catalogue) that occurred during a very interesting orbital configuration (Figure 23) as it was well connected to Earth and STEREO-A like GLE74 and clearly observed remotely by a broad range of observatories. A preliminary trajectory analysis showed that the CME was directed at Parker Solar Probe then situated

at 0.6 AU, thereby providing an excellent opportunity to study an efficient particle accelerator in the inner heliosphere.

Figure 23: Left panel: Image from Solar-MACH tool (Gieseler et al. 2023). Top view of the ecliptic plane from the North on the 8 June 2024. Red, green, yellow, purple and blue lines corresponds respectively to magnetic field lines connected to STEREO-A, the Earth, BepiColombo, PSP, SO.

3.2.1 Solar and interplanetary conditions

A M9.8 flare occurred on 08 June 2024 in AR13697 close to the West limb of the Sun (S17W72). Preliminary analysis of EUV data from the SDO reveals a main CME eruption with clear post-flare loops as well as smaller scale transients caught up in the sheath during the initial expansion of the main event. Coronagraphic observations of the CME by SoHO and STEREO-A are of high quality revealing a clear broad CME shock.

On this date a very strong SEP event ($E > 100$ MeV) was recorded at Earth by GOES SOHO/ERPHIN and SOHO/ERNE and was characterized as a sub-GLE (Poluianov et al. 2017). Given the most optimal magnetic connection STEREO-A also recorded enhanced proton and electron fluxes together with He, CNO and Fe that were also measured at this time.

One of the most interesting features of this event is the long lasting period of low radiation levels prior to this event that can be used to infer onset of energetic particles. This onset analysis remains to be done through different techniques. In contrast to GLE74, the event is also associated with quiet interplanetary conditions prior to the event providing a justification to the use of a simple Parker spiral to model the interplanetary magnetic field.

3.2.2 3-D shock reconstruction:

An expanding bubble was clearly visible around the flaring site by 01:37UT (left panel of 24) and later expanding into the coronagraph images). The expansion of this structure could be fitted in 3-D again using the shock-fitting technique of Rouillard et al. (2016). The results of this fitting are superposed on the STEREO image in the right-hand panel of Figure 24. This fitting technique provided, as for the May event, the shock location and expansion speed over the entire expanding surface.

To obtain additional shock parameters we used again the coronal model by Predictive Sciences Inc

Figure 24: Left panel: Image from EUVI-A on the 8 June 2024 at 01:37:00 UT. Right panel: Same image with a superposed fitted shock in orange.

called MAST¹⁸. Following the technique of Rouillard et al. (2016); Kouloumvakos et al. (2019), we then derive the 3-D distribution of the Mach number, shock geometry and shock geometry on the entire shock surface (24).

In order to determine whether the shock was magnetically connected to specific points of SEP measurements, we exploit a combination of the background MHD coronal model and an interplanetary magnetic field model to trace field lines backwards from the probe to the photosphere. For the analysis we assumed again a Parker spiral for the background interplanetary magnetic field to establish magnetic connectivity. As in the previous analysis, we then extracted shock parameters along that field line as a function of time.

We found that around the solar particle release time, the Earth was connected magnetically to a strong quasi-perpendicular shock. STEREO-A connected a couple of minutes later than Earth to a strong shock. Near-Earth spacecraft and STEREO-A measured a powerful SEP event with Earth measuring the first energetic particles slightly early than Earth. All other probes were connected later to a much weaker part of the shock and measured much weaker SEPs. A next step in the analysis will be to quantify the acceleration process of energetic particles from the shock properties modelled here following a similar approach to that carried out in Afanasiev et al. (2018).

3.2.3 Preliminary conclusions on the analysis of the 8 June 2024:

The analysis of Event 166 has begun. We have carried out a reconstruction and modelling of the shock associated with this event and we have shown that it was connected magnetically to Earth around the estimated release time of this sub-GLE. At that time the shock was already strong and quasi-perpendicular offering favourable conditions for the acceleration of particles. Unlike the May event (GLE74), the interplanetary conditions are more simple, the onset of the SEP occurs during very quiet conditions with low SEP backgrounds. In addition the interplanetary magnetic field is more likely to be a Parker spiral.

We should be able for this event to model the shock propagation from its region of formation, as already done, all the way to PSP where a preliminary analysis of the in situ data shows that a shock

¹⁸https://www.predsci.com/mhdweb/summary_plots.php

Figure 25: Evolution of derived shock parameters along magnetic field lines from STEREO-A (red), Earth (green), PSP (purple), BepiColombo (yellow), and SO (blue) as a function of time. Left panels: from top to bottom, shock speed V_{sh} , Mach Alfvénic number M_A , Hoffman-Teller speed V_{HT} , Alfvén speed V_a . Right panels: from top to bottom, magnetic field obliquity θ_{BN} , Magnetosonic Mach number M_{MS} , compression ratio X_R , sound speed V_S .

and flux-rope passed by the spacecraft at the estimated impact time. This will allow us to obtain a more detailed model of the shock evolution from its origin to the inner heliosphere and its role in the acceleration of particles.

4 Conclusions and Outlook

WP4 has continued its analysis of the solar context of $>100\text{MeV}$ SEPs. For each event in the $>100\text{MeV}$ catalogue, we have provided a list of the remote sensing signatures of solar energetic particles detected at different energies of the electromagnetic spectrum. We presented preliminary results based on the statistical analysis of the SEPs and the different solar signatures. For each electromagnetic signature, we also listed future improvements that could be added to the analysis for future releases of the catalogue.

We have begun the in-depth analysis of a subset of events that were identified in D4.1 as strategic

for the main science goals of the SPEARHEAD project namely to better understand the acceleration process and transport of the most energetic solar particles. The work is on-going and will be the subject of dedicated scientific articles to be published in year 2 and 3 of the project.

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